

AN ANALYSIS OF VOLATILITY OF RETAIL PRODUCT PRICES DURING THE LOCKDOWN PERIOD

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1. Abstract

High frequency price data collected daily for a basket of retail products covering common household categories can be used to obtain interesting insights into the volatility of prices. Additional insight can be derived to infer information about the sources of products through the correlation of individual product prices to the basket. This paper uses data describes a method to arrive at a high frequency, personalized, real measure of inflation and to use the data to begin to understand the causes of price volatility.

Keywords

Volatility, Inflation, High-frequency, Real-time, Online prices, Lockdown

2. Introduction

Consumer Price Inflation (CPI), [reported monthly \(MOSPI, n.d.\)in India](#), can be significantly at variance with an individual's experience of that metric. Such a variance is understandable given the averaging of the consumption patterns across a large population that is used in calculating CPI. The relatively slow periodicity of this index also makes it much less usable in light of the far more frequent changes to prices that happen in real life.

This creates an opportunity for a more personalized inflation index which measures the real inflation as can be experienced by an individual consumer using real data that such a consumer might encounter. This can lead to different approach to measuring aggregate CPI, at a country or state level, by using averages of inflation experienced by individual consumers than inflation of an average consumer. Such an approach can easily factor in the varying circumstances, lifestyles and other aspects of individual consumers and result in a more accurate measure in the aggregate. This approach, impossible in the past due to the difficulty of obtaining data and computing inflation at an individual level is now feasible due to the significantly increased adoption of online shopping, at least for the key consumption expenditures, the ability to create a personalized, real basket of goods, and the consequent ability to obtain real-time prices for such a basket. Additional context to this experiment can be found at (Tanksali, Posts on Real Price Index, n.d.). Three outcomes of this could be:

1. A real view of inflation, completely personalized to an individual
2. An aggregate CPI based on the average of individual consumer inflations as against inflation of an averaged consumer
3. A high-frequency measure of inflation, updated at least daily, of key retail consumption

An experiment to test this hypothesis was started with a single individual's consumption basket. While this will expand into a multi-user experiment, the COVID-19 imposed lockdown intervened during the experiment. This, however, gave the opportunity to monitor the prices

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as they changed through the course of this lockdown. The experiment is still in its early stages, but this initial set of data is interesting in and of itself.

The basket of 80 products, with prices obtained daily over a 3 month period resulted in a rich set of data on how prices rose as the lockdown kicked in and how they started easing as the lockdown was relaxed. This is an analysis on the behaviour of the prices of the basket of 80 products over a 91 day period covering the entire lockdown period in India.

Of particular interest would be the dichotomy between the statements of the [RBI](#) and the sentiments [expressed by consumers](#). The analysis in this paper supports the consumer sentiment and indicates a need for a continued and more detailed study in this area.

3. Literature Survey

There are several studies around measuring prices, particularly food prices, intended to analyse and inform agricultural production and pricing. The study by (H Jordaan, 2007) focusing on crop prices in South Africa is quite relevant. However, it covers a range of prices dating back up to 10 years and for just a few products. The study by (Salome Gelashvili, 2007) on measuring food price volatility in Georgia also considers prices other than commodities and evaluates its impact on the CPI for Georgia. The current analysis does not consider aspects other than commodity prices. The study by (S. AVOUYI-DOVI, 2014) also provides an alternative way to consider price volatility. All these studies use long term prices, obtained as historical data. The use of online prices in an on-demand mode is studied by (Ritwik Banerjee, 2018) and is used to predict inflation

These studies have provided the context to analyse the data generated in this experiment and to evolve a new measure that seems to provide additional information.

4. Data

A basket of 80 products were identified based on actual personal consumption on one individual. These covered all the items of purchase in that household in a month, across multiple categories of consumption. These 80 products could be classified as follows into categories.

Category	Number of Products
Cleaning supplies	6
Cosmetics	3
Dairy	4
Fruits and Vegetables	24
Hygiene	7
Packaged food	13
Staples	23

Table 1

Each of these products were associate with a product available from a popular e-commerce provider. The price of each product was fetched once a day and recorded. There could be instances where a fetch might fail or not result in meaningful data as this information was being obtained as a end user, via an automated script. There could be instances where the site blocked such an attempt to collect info or there were other technical errors or potentially the product was not available at that time. A second attempt was made to fill any gaps from

the first fetch. Any gaps that remained after the second fetch were left as failures for the day and the most recent price for that product was used to compute the total price for the basket.

Each product had an associated quantity and a number of units needed to allow a total price to be obtained which matched the actual consumption of that household. The attempt to get real data could be met with this as that consumer could potentially order the basket of products on that day to meet their family's need for the month and pay the exact price of that basket on that day. This would hence provide an absolutely accurate assessment of inflation as experienced by that consumer.

The data collection was started from 29th Feb 2020, Leap Day 2020 and continues at the time of this paper. The analysis is for the period 29th Feb 2020 to 31st May 2020. 31 May provides a convenient end point for this phase of the study as it was the last day of the lockdown, with the relaxations ("Unlock 1.0") beginning from 1st June.

There were 93 days of data that was collected. On 3 days the number of prices fetched was below 50% and hence these 3 days - 16, 25 and 26 March – are excluded from the bulk of the analysis. These dates correspond to the start of the corporate switch to Work From Home (16 March) and the official lockdown start (25 March) resulting in both shortages of products as well as unprecedented demand on the e-commerce provider resulting in unavailability of pricing information.

The processed data is available online in a daily updated format at <https://realpi.tanksali.com>

The total number of prices collected were 7036 over the 90 days used in the analysis. That is more than 78 prices per day or 97.7% of prices being fetched every day giving a high degree of freshness to the data as well as robustness.

Figure 1

5. Methodology and Results

The total price of the basket of products used had a minimum value of ₹15,902.00 on the 1st of March and reaching a high of ₹17,414.00 on the 25th of April. The price of the basket each day over the entire period, with a lockdown phase indicator overlay gives a clear picture of how the price can instinctively be correlated with the phases.

The grey line represents the daily prices and the red line represents the smoothed prices using a 7-day moving average. The start of the ramp is on the day most offices in Bengaluru declared a work-from-home policy for their employees and the Government announced a partial closure of large gatherings. The prices rapidly reached a high ₹17,261.00 on 31st March and remained at a high with minor variations till 1st of May, with a peak on the 25th of

April when the basket reached ₹17,414.00. It started easing gradually after that but has remained approximately 6 % higher than those prevailing at the start of the study.

Figure 2

Inflation relative to start of experiment at key milestones

A summary of straightforward rise in prices, relative to the start of the experiment, gives a clear picture of how end users found prices.

Date	Milestone	Basket total price, ₹	Inflation, %
1 Mar	Start of experiment	15902	Base – 0
14 Mar	Start of pre-lockdown	16062	1.00%
24 Mar	Start of first lockdown	17126	7.69%
15 Apr	Start of lockdown 2	17287	8.80%
25 Apr	Peak price	17414	9.50%
4 May	Start of lockdown 3	17369	9.22%
17 May	Start of final lockdown	17118	7.64%
31 May	End of lockdown	16864	6.04%

Table 2

Volatility of prices

This section looks at individual products and prices, to get an insight beyond the aggregate.

Price variations

The rise in prices for the 77 products was measured as a simple $\max(\text{price})/\min(\text{price})$ to give a simple first level range indicator of how much change a product had. There was one product, Beans, which had a ratio of 7.25 for its price range and a second, Capsicum, which had a ratio of 5.40. The rest had an average range of 1.55. The unusually high ratio is due to the low price these have in normal times which makes small absolute changes end up with high relative swings.

Figure 3

A second measure of volatility was to use standard deviation. This showed considerably more variation than the previous range measure. The highest standard deviation was for Rice, the primary staple of the region. This product had a modest max/min ratio of 1.29 but there were several swings of that magnitude on either side of the mean to give this high stddev.

Figure 4

There is a third measure of volatility that makes intuitive sense and is to do with the number of times the price changed in this period for a given product. The constant price products in the earlier section would have a Change Count of 0, for example. Tomatoes had the highest number of price changes in this period – a remarkable 40 times within this 90 day period. While conventional measures like standard deviation provide one view, instinctive measures like the frequent price changes, which do matter to end consumers, can serve as an equally valuable companion.

Figure 5

Using these different measures gives us different perspectives on the way the prices changed. A selection of products that highlight the different views that the three measures of max/min, standard deviation and change count provide is in the table below.

Product	Atta 5kg (anon brand)	Rice 5kg (anon brand)	Besan 500g	Peanuts 1kg	Green Chilli 100g	Beetroot 250g
Product Code	TFBA0039	TFBA0040	TFBA0043	TFBA0045	TFBA0066	TFBA0071
Count of						
Prices	90	90	88	90	90	90
MRP	300	350	90	220	7.5	15
Min Price, ₹	273	270	40	122	4	4
Max Price, ₹	300	349	70	182	8	13
Average						
Price, ₹	286.04	303.73	54.32	146.62	5.18	8.21
TrimMean						
(10%), ₹	286.00	303.16	54.25	146.09	5.12	8.23
Max/Min	1.10	1.29	1.75	1.49	2.00	3.25
StdDevP	9.15	28.63	11.53	17.69	0.84	2.18
Change#	8	8	5	5	24	20
Correlation						
with Basket	0.32	0.35	0.05	0.39	-0.29	0.20
	Low	Moderate	High	Moderate	High	Very high
	max/min,	max/min,	max/min,	max/min,	max/min,	max/min,
	high StdDev,	high StdDev,	high StdDev,	high StdDev,	low StdDev,	low StdDev,
	low price	low price	low price	low price	high price	high price
Summary	change count	change count	change count	change count	change count	change count

Table 3

The prices of all the products (the ones in the sample as well as the remaining) remained at or below the “official” MRP² during this period.

The Exceptions

There were a few products which stood out for having absolutely no change in price through this period when prices for some items were even doubling. These exceptional products are

Product	Price, ₹	Change
Bread	39	No change throughout
Coffee decoction	135	No change throughout
Britannia Marie Biscuits	15	No change throughout

Figure 6

Price Correlation

Another analysis can be performed on how closely the individual product prices mirrored the trend in the overall basket. This throws up a few very interesting aspects. There are 9 products which are negatively correlated with the overall basket. These are products whose prices effectively moved downwards as the prices of the rest of the basket moved upwards. These negatively correlated products are milk, several vegetables, and grapes. The highest correlation with the price increase is with packaged food (cereals etc) and hygiene products, indicating that these are the contributing products that drove the basket prices higher.

² Locally sourced produce does not have an MRP

The interesting aspect of the negatively correlated set of products is that they are all locally produced. The largest dairy in the state is in the city and there were [newspaper reports of fall in demand](#) as no dairy products were being bought by restaurants and the food business which were all closed. The vegetables were all locally produced on the outskirts of the city from where transport was permitted. Grapes were understandable as Bengaluru has a very large number of vineyards in the North of the city. The fact that locally produced products will probably have an oversupply and manufactured products that need to be transported from elsewhere will be scarce makes instinctive sense when all forms of transport are being restricted. The data bears this out consistently over the entire period.

Figure 7

The prices, therefore, show the following characteristics:

1. Prices have remained below MRP through the period
 - a. MRPs have not changed, from the manufacturers side, in this period
2. Prices of local goods have reduced
 - a. Anecdotally, prices for local produce had crashed significantly more than reflected on the e-commerce portal
3. The price increase is very likely largely opportunistic
 - a. The increased prices are intended, quite possibly, to offset the increased cost of stocking and delivery while following the heightened sanitization procedures

6. Conclusion

The experiment to measure Real Price Index, as experienced by individual consumers, had the by-product of generating a rich price data set during the lockdown period. The analysis shows that overall inflation for consumers reached a high of 9.50% over a base of the start of the 90 day period. The use of a measure like price change count can help add additional information in analysing price volatility. The information obtained by analysing correlation of individual product prices with the basket and their movement in relation to MRP provides significant insight into sources of the products and potentially about the supply chain.

There are many opportunities to study this further, in the context of this brief experiment, to continue this further and understand pricing volatility in a high frequency data environment. The larger experiment to uncover the Real Price Index and obtain personalized, personally experienced, measure of inflation and thereby arrive at a new form of aggregate CPI needs to continue.

7. References

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